

Decoding structural characteristics of fluorinated graphene via Computer-Aided spectroscopic analysis

Petr Lazar^a, Vítězslav Hrubý^a, Martin Petr^a, Zdeněk Baďura^{a,b}, Giorgio Zoppellaro^{a,b}

^a Regional Centre of Advanced Technologies and Materials, Czech Advanced Technology and Research Institute (CATRIN), Palacký University Olomouc, Šlechtitelů 27, 783 71, Olomouc, Czech Republic

^b Nanotechnology Centre, Centre for Energy and Environmental Technologies, VŠB-Technical University of Ostrava, 17. Listopadu 2172/15, Ostrava-Poruba, 708 00, Czech Republic

^c IT4Innovations, VŠB-Technical University of Ostrava, 17. listopadu 2172/15 Ostrava-Poruba, 70800, Czech Republic

ABSTRACT

Fluorographene, a monolayer form of carbon monofluoride, is a fluorinated graphene derivative with intriguing properties and serves as a crucial precursor for synthesizing various graphene-based materials. Understanding its structural and chemical characteristics is essential for harnessing its potential, yet many aspects of its structure remain far from fully understood. Common spectroscopic methods such as infrared spectroscopy (IR) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) face challenges in precisely assigning measured binding energies and IR signals to specific atomic configurations. To address these ambiguities, we combined ab initio density functional theory calculations with experimental approaches to model spectroscopic signatures of various conformations and structural defects in fluorographene. Additionally, we investigated the structures of partially fluorinated graphene derivatives, C₂F and C₄F. Our theoretical insights guided the structural interpretation of an in-depth characterization of two typical commercially available graphite fluoride samples using multiple techniques, including Fourier-transformed IR, XPS with Ar⁺ ion beam etching, electron paramagnetic resonance, and nuclear magnetic resonance. Our findings highlight the valuable role of low-frequency IR spectroscopy and establish a foundation for identifying key structural features through a combination of theoretical calculations and spectroscopic experiments, applicable not only to fluorographene and fluorinated graphite but also in exploring structural characteristics of other two-dimensional and layered materials.

1. Introduction

The structure of a material plays a crucial role in determining its physical and chemical properties at both macroscopic and atomic scales. Defects, for example, can degrade the performance of electronic devices - an issue recognized since the early days of the electronics industry. Their impact is even more pronounced in quantum materials, such as superconducting qubits, which are highly sensitive to a very small number (sometimes even a single one) of defects of a specific type [1,2]. Although a plethora of surface analysis techniques exists to characterize the composition, structure, and chemistry of materials, the assignment of measured signal to specific defects and structural motifs remains challenging. This often leads to inconsistencies or even misleading material characterization.

A prime example of such complexity is carbon monofluoride, a fully fluorinated member of the layered fluorinated graphite family, where fluorine atoms are covalently bonded to an extended two-dimensional

carbon framework. First synthesized in 1934 [3], carbon monofluoride and its sub-fluorinated variants have been extensively studied, leading to numerous applications of graphite fluorides, including use as conversion cathodes in high-energy-density lithium primary (non-rechargeable) batteries, solid lubricants, and hydrophobic coatings [4–6]. Interest in these materials has been reignited in 2011 with the discovery and successful isolation of fluorographene (FG), a two-dimensional analogue of bulk carbon monofluoride [7,8]. Unlike graphene, FG is an insulating material due to fluorine atoms altering the carbon hybridization from sp^2 to sp^3 , which opens a large electronic band-gap of almost 8 eV [9,10] and an optical gap of ~ 5.7 eV [11]. This insulating nature makes FG valuable for power electronics, high-temperature electronics, and commercial battery technology [12]. In addition, FG serves as a suitable precursor for a controllable and up-scalable synthesis of a broad portfolio of graphene derivatives [13–17].

Despite extensive research, the structure of carbon monofluoride

* Corresponding author. Regional Centre of Advanced Technologies and Materials, Czech Advanced Technology and Research Institute (CATRIN), Palacký University Olomouc, Šlechtitelů 27, 783 71, Olomouc, Czech Republic.

E-mail address: michal.otyepka@upol.cz (M. Otyepka).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2025.120567>

Received 25 May 2025; Received in revised form 23 June 2025; Accepted 23 June 2025

Available online 24 June 2025

0008-6223/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

remains far from fully understood. The first structural model was proposed by Rüdorff and Rüdorff in 1947, describing the material as composed of covalent C–F single bonds [18]. In this model, the fluorine atoms protrude axially above and below the carbon framework in an alternating pattern such that each C–F bond is oriented opposite to its three nearest neighbors. In this arrangement, carbon monofluoride adopts a hexagonal crystal structure. Although this original crystal structure is considered the “conclusive” structural model, various structural polymorphs and motifs have been proposed to account for discrepancies in experimental observations. These polymorphs include chair, tricycle, boat, twist boat, armchair, and zigzag conformations of the carbon backbone, as well as mixtures of these conformations in bulk stacking [19]. Additionally, Walder and Alam suggested that boat-type conformers might coexist with chair-type conformers even within individual six-membered framework rings [20]. In addition to structural uncertainties, recent studies on fluorinated graphite materials have highlighted the crucial role of lattice defects in determining the properties of FG. The midgap states associated with defects were responsible for the unexpected photoluminescence of FG at energies below its optical gap, as reported in early studies [21,22]. Medved’ et al. further confirmed the presence of radical centers, specifically fluorine vacancies, in FG through electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) experiments, demonstrating their significant influence on FG chemistry [23]. Tacca and Plenio identified the carbon-and-fluorine vacancy in FG as a promising candidate for nanomechanical resonators, drawing parallels to nitrogen-vacancy centers in diamond [24]. More recently, our study revealed a critical interplay between solvent molecules and radical centers in FG, leading to the generation of spin-active states in FG/acetone dispersions upon UV irradiation [25].

Beyond the fully fluorinated form, a diverse range of structures with lower degrees of fluorination exist, offering significant technological potential. By adjusting the graphite content, fluorine concentration, and C–F bonding characteristics, these materials can be fine-tuned for enhanced chemical and thermal stability, optimized tribological properties, and controlled discharge potentials in battery applications. However, much like carbon monofluoride, the structural details of these materials remain elusive. The variety of proposed structural models and persistent discrepancies suggest that our understanding, largely based on the hexagonal crystal structure of carbon monofluoride, is still incomplete. A notable example is polydicarbon monofluoride (C_2F)_n, first discovered by Kita et al., in 1979 [26]. Based on X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) patterns, it was initially assigned a monoclinic crystal structure with covalent C–F bonds. However, other studies reported that during fluorination of graphite in the presence of HF, the process remained reversible up to the C_2F composition, and the planarity of carbon sheets was preserved [27]. In this model, fluorine atoms were thought to attach to carbon atoms through weak, so-called “semi-ionic” bonds [28]. Later, Touhara et al. proposed yet another structure, a hexagonal crystal lattice in which fluorine atoms were covalently bonded, with all carbon atoms adopting sp^3 hybridization [29]. The presence and precise nature of semi-ionic fluorine remain elusive, yet this bonding type continues to be linked to specific features in X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) spectra of graphite fluoride-based materials. These findings underscore the need for advanced characterization techniques or their strategic combinations to accurately distinguish both the lattice structure and defect nature in fluorinated graphites.

In this paper, we combine ab initio density functional theory (DFT) calculations with experimental techniques to identify and rationalize spectroscopic fingerprints of various conformations, structural motifs, and defects in FG. We apply these fingerprints obtained from theoretical calculations to analyze two commercial graphite fluoride samples. We deliberately pick commercial samples of FG as these are typical materials used in many related experiments in which an insufficiently defined phase composition may cause issues. The samples were characterized by FT-IR in the far infrared region, ion-discharged XPS before and after

treatment with Ar^+ ion beam etching. EPR was employed to assess the presence of radical defects in the studied materials, and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to gauge the topology of the samples. Solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) unraveled their degree of disorder and estimated the F/C ratios of their fluorinated structures based on the contents of CF, CF_2 , and CF_3 groups in ^{19}F spectra. Using DFT, we perform an energetic analysis of pristine FG and its two most common conformations, chair and boat, and evaluation of the formation energies of various types of lattice defects: fluorine vacancy (radical defect), fluorine divacancy, carbon-and-fluorine vacancy, misplaced fluorine atom, Stone-Wales defect, and partially defluorinated FG. Following this, we simulate both XPS and IR spectroscopic fingerprints of the chair and boat structure, as well as various lattice defects. We also investigate the structures of partially fluorinated FG, including C_2F formed by one-sided fluorination, (C_2F)_n, a double-decked structure in which fluorine atoms are inserted into every second graphite layer (F-diamane structure) [30], and C_4F , a compound with interleaved hexagonal arrays, where fluorine atoms are covalently bonded to single carbon atoms across planar sp^2 hybridized graphene layers [31]. This phase has been observed in partially fluorinated samples or within the core domains of the particles when the diffusion of fluorine during the fluorination process is limited [31,32]. Finally, we apply theoretical insights to the interpretation of experimental spectra, providing a comprehensive understanding of fluorinated graphite materials.

2. Methods

2.1. Theoretical calculations

The projector-augmented wave (PAW) method, as implemented in the Vienna ab-initio simulation package (VASP) suite, was used for the calculations [33,34]. The energy cutoff for the plane-wave expansion was set to 500 eV. The total energy and forces were calculated by applying the *meta*-GGA functional R2SCAN [35]. R2SCAN is recently developed functional combining transferable accuracy from the exact constraint satisfaction of SCAN (strongly constrained and appropriately normed) functional with improved numerical efficiency [36]. SCAN provided an improved description of vibrational properties (phonon spectra) over standard semi-local functionals [37], and R2SCAN should retain this behavior.

The fluorographene sheet was modeled by a 6×6 supercell (72 carbon and 72 fluorine atoms). For each initial orientation, the local minimum of the energy was found by force-relaxation of atomic coordinates and in-plane lattice vectors. The periodically repeated sheets were separated by at least 16 Å of vacuum, and a $3 \times 3 \times 1$ *k*-point grid was used to sample the Brillouin zone. The elements of the force-constant matrix for the calculation of vibrational modes were determined utilizing a finite displacement approach. The IR intensity of each mode was calculated using the matrix of Born effective charges, which describes the change of atoms’ polarizabilities with respect to an external electric field [38]. Born effective charges were calculated from the response to finite electric fields. The calculated line spectra were broadened by a Lorentzian resolution function with a width of 15 cm^{-1} . The thermodynamic stability of various types of lattice defects was assessed by their formation energy. The formation energy E_f for a defect in FG is defined as

$$E_f = E_d - E_{FG} + n_C \mu_C + n_F \mu_F$$

where E_d is the total energy of the supercell with the defect, E_{FG} is the total energy of the pristine (bulk) supercell, n_C and n_F are the respective numbers of carbon and fluorine atoms that are added or removed from FG to form the defect, μ_C and μ_F are the corresponding chemical potentials. We consider either a carbon-rich or fluorine-rich environment, which sets the bounds of the chemical potential. In the fluorine-rich environment, we assume that defective FG is in the equilibrium with

F_2 and set $\mu_F = \frac{1}{2}E(F_2)$, i.e., set μ_F to half of the total energy of a F_2 molecule. The chemical potential of carbon is then calculated from the difference between the energy of the pristine fluorographene primitive cell (μ_{FG}) and the fluorine chemical potential, $\mu_C = \mu_{FG} - \mu_F$. In the carbon-rich environment, we set μ_C to that of a carbon atom in the graphene primitive cell and obtain the fluorine chemical potential as the difference $\mu_F = \mu_{FG} - \mu_C$.

For the calculation of the x-ray photoemission process, two types of methodologies can be applied to obtain the core level binding energies: the initial and final state method. In the initial state methods, only the energy level of the core electron is considered. In the final state method, a core hole is explicitly included in the calculation, and the electronic structure of the system is relaxed in its presence. We calculated the binding energies using the final state method as the total energy difference between a calculation with the core hole and a ground state calculation. The FHI-aims code was used for this calculation; FHI-aims is an all-electron, full-potential code that treats core electrons explicitly and at the same level as the valence electrons [39]. The tight basis set was utilized because it provided the total energies converged to sub-meV accuracy. A similar computational approach was successfully applied for resolving structural features of nitrogen doping in graphene [40]. The total energies for the final state method were calculated by applying the SCAN functional. The structures were taken from the VASP calculation.

2.2. Materials and experiments

To directly support our DFT results with experimental data, two commercial samples of graphite fluorides (GFs) differing greatly in their optical properties were thoroughly characterized. The first graphite fluoride codenamed GFA1 was purchased from ACS Material (product number GT1F0020). The second material, GFC2L, was purchased as lubricant-type graphite fluoride from Coreychem company (China). The materials differ greatly in their appearance; GFA1 is grey powder (Fig. S1a) while GFC2L appears off-white (Fig. S1b). The declared particle size of GFA1 was 1–10 μm and the sample appeared homogeneous even when probed by optical microscope at $10\times$ magnification (Fig. S1c). GFC2L was evidently inhomogeneous, appearing as large white crystalline particles mixed with numerous dark particles of various shapes and diameters (Fig. S1d). To further specify the optoelectronic properties of the materials, UV-VIS DRS spectra of both materials were recorded. The bandgap energies were estimated to be 2.5 eV for GFA1 and 5.76 eV for GFC2L using the Tauc method, considering a direct bandgap of the tested GFs (Fig. S2). While the value for GFC2L is consistent with the bandgap of pristine high-quality FG [11], the optical gap of GFA1 is much lower reflecting its darker color.

While appearing homogeneous, powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) of GFA1 revealed a minor presence of the graphite phase (Fig. S3a). On the other hand, the phase composition of GFC2L appeared as clean graphite fluoride despite its apparent inhomogeneities (Fig. S3b). Such inhomogeneities can therefore be ascribed to less fluorinated particles of graphite, but the pure graphite phase is not present. The interlayer spacing was found to be 6.05 \AA for GFA1 and 6.81 \AA for GFC2L. The spacing of GFA1 is close to that of the ideal $(\text{CF})_n$, which has the theoretical value of 5.70–5.92 \AA depending on the stacking sequence [41]. The wider d-spacing of GFC2L can be attributed to warping and bending of the individual flakes (see NMR results, Fig. S4) rather than a presence of greater amount of the $(\text{C}_2\text{F})_n$ phase, because latter effect can be ruled out based on the results discussed below. Furthermore, reflections from the (110) plane were observed in the case of GFA1 [42].

2.3. Characterization techniques

Far infrared spectra were measured on a Nicolet™ iS50 FTIR Spectrometer (Thermo Scientific™) using a built-in diamond attenuated total reflectance (ATR) module. Before the measurement, the diamond ATR

crystal was cleaned with EtOH, and the background was scanned. Then, the sample was deposited onto the crystal and pressed towards the face of the crystal. The spectrum was then acquired with automatically applied ATR correction in the range between 200 cm^{-1} to 1600 cm^{-1} by summing up 32 scans.

The XPS measurements were performed using the Nexsa G2 XPS system (Thermo Scientific) equipped with a monochromatic Al $K\alpha$ X-ray source ($h\nu = 1486.6$ eV). When needed, prior to the XPS measurements, Ar^+ ion etching was conducted to remove the surface layer of the materials. The etching was performed using a low-energy Ar^+ ion beam with an energy of 500 eV, and the current was maintained at a low setting to minimize surface damage. Each etching cycle was carried out for 30 s. Spectra acquisition was conducted under ultra-high vacuum conditions (1.2×10^{-7} Pa) at room temperature (20 °C). The analysis area on each sample was a circular spot with a diameter of 200 μm . Survey spectra were recorded with a pass energy of 150.00 eV and a step size of 1.0 eV, while high-resolution spectra were collected with a pass energy of 50.00 eV and a step size of 0.1 eV. During all measurements, a charge neutralization system was employed to prevent charging effects, ensuring accurate peak positions and reliable quantitative results. Charge neutralization was achieved by using dual-beam charge compensation (low-energy electrons combined with low-energy ions) effectively neutralizing the charge build-up on the surface of the sample. Data acquisition and analysis were performed using Avantage software (version 6.8.1). Deconvolution of HR-XPS spectra was carried out using MagicPlot software after subtracting the Shirley background in Origin-Pro software.

Solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectra were acquired using JEOL spectrometer JNM-ECZ400R with a magnetic field of 9.4 T (working frequency 399.8 MHz for ^1H , 376.3 MHz for ^{19}F , and 100.5 MHz for ^{13}C NMR). All the measurements were conducted at 18 kHz magic angle spinning (MAS) frequency using a 3.2 mm MAS probe. ^{19}F spectra were acquired using a single pulse TOSS (total suppression of spinning sidebands) technique with a relaxation delay of 5 s. ^{13}C cross-polarization (CP) MAS spectra were acquired using $a^{19}\text{F}$ irradiation offset of -130 ppm, a contact time of 1 ms, and a relaxation delay of 5 s. Phase corrections involving both zero-order and first-order adjustments were applied to all spectra using Delta 6.1.0 software (JEOL). For ^{19}F spectra, additional baseline corrections were applied using OriginPro software. The deconvolution of all the spectra was conducted using MagicPlot software. Integral values of distinct ^{19}F regions used for the F/C ratio estimation were obtained as the sum of the absolute areas of the individual components obtained by the deconvolution of the spectra. The chemical shift values were referenced to CFCl_3 and TMS for ^{19}F and ^{13}C domains, respectively.

The SEM images were obtained by Scios 2 Dual Beam (ThermoFisher SCIENTIFIC) with an accelerating voltage of 5 kV. The samples were prepared by dispersing in acetonitrile using ultrasonication for 2 min. Subsequently, they were dropped onto on a carbon-coated copper grid, left for drying and attached to an aluminium holder using double-sided carbon tape.

EPR spectra were collected on X-band (~ 9.14 – 9.17 GHz) spectrometer JEOL JES-X-320 equipped by variable He temperature set-up ES-CT470 apparatus. The experimental temperature was set to 90 K. The quality factor (Q) was kept above 7500. As a sample holder was used high purity quartz tubes (Suprasil, Wilmad, ≤ 0.5 OD), and the accuracy of the g-values was determined by comparison with a $\text{Mn}^{2+}/\text{MgO}$ standard (JEOL standard). The microwave power was set to 1.0 mW. The modulation width of 0.7 mT and the modulation frequency of 100 kHz were used. All EPR spectra were collected with a time constant of 30 ms and sweep time of 2 min with three accumulations to improve the signal-to-noise ratio.

3. Results and discussion

FG is a simple binary compound, but many different structural

polymorphs of fluorinated graphene/graphite have been discussed over the years. The proposed polymorphs include chair, tricycle, boat, twist boat, armchair, and zigzag conformations of the carbon framework [19]. The generally accepted model of FG is a chair-like conformation in which fluorine atoms protrude axially above and below the carbon framework in an alternating pattern (Fig. 1a) [18]. A boat-like conformer with the fluorine atoms alternating in pairs on both sides of the carbon atom layer was proposed in mid-70 based on dipolar second moments of the static ^{19}F NMR lines [43,44]. Boat-type conformation is supposed to be difficult to form in fluorographene because fluorine atoms bonded on one side of the carbon atom layer in pairs are repelled by electrostatic repulsion. According to our calculation, the total energy of the boat conformer is 0.11 eV per atom higher than that of the chair conformer. This value is in good agreement with a high-level quantum mechanical calculation based on the combination of the exact-exchange (EXX) and correlation energy in the random phase approximation (RPA), which yielded an energy difference of 0.20 eV/atom [41]. Thus, the chair conformation is the ground state of FG, serving as the basis for the subsequent point defect calculations.

3.1. Defects in fluorographene and their formation energy

The formation of defects is an endothermic process, with defect formation energies depending on the defect type and chemical potential (Table 1). The most basic point defect is the fluorine vacancy, V_{F} (Fig. 1c). The V_{F} vacancy leaves a C atom with a dangling sp^3 bond, resulting in the creation of a radical site with an unpaired spin. The V_{F} site has a net magnetic moment of 1 μB , and localized defect states appear in the band gap, thus the presence of V_{F} defects was invoked to explain magnetic activity of some FG based materials [23,45]. The formation energy of the V_{F} defect is 1.58 eV in the carbon-rich environment and becomes higher in a more fluorine-rich environment.

The fluorine divacancy $V_{2\text{F}}$ is created by removing two fluorine atoms at neighboring carbon sites (Fig. 1d). This defect is more favorable than V_{F} in carbon-rich conditions. The spins on two carbon atoms become paired, so the system is diamagnetic. In carbon-rich conditions, its formation is by 0.65 eV more favorable than the formation of V_{F} , which is, on the other hand, preferred in a fluorine-rich environment. Thus, the environment (carbon chemical potential) can play a significant role in presence of larger graphitic domains even in nominally fully fluorinated graphite [11].

A V_{CF} defect stands for missing a carbon atom and fluorine atom at the same lattice position (Fig. 1e). This defect lowers the symmetry of the system to C_{3v} , and three dangling carbon bonds around the defect are

Table 1

The formation energies (in eV) of various point defects in FG in the carbon-rich and fluorine-rich environment. See text for details.

Defect	Carbon-rich	Fluorine-rich
V_{F}	1.58	3.38
$V_{2\text{F}}$	0.93	4.52
V_{CF}	4.27	4.27
Stone-Wales	3.37	3.37
F inverted	3.10	3.10

created. This defect is fundamentally interesting because its symmetry and electronic structure are reminiscent to those of a NV center in diamond [24], which has been proposed as a suitable candidate for the implementation of a qubit [46]. Its formation energy is high, 4.27 eV. In natural graphite fluoride, its formation may proceed by partial decomposition to CF_2 due to the reaction between the two neighboring layers of $(\text{CF})_n$ at high temperatures [47]. Such defects could also be fabricated by methods such as ion implantation and laser ablation.

We also consider two defects that result in two adjacent F atoms being on the same side of the carbon layer: the Stone-Wales (SW) defect and the inverted F atom (Fig. 1f and g). The SW defect involves the reconstruction of four adjacent hexagonal rings into two pentagon and two heptagon rings. The SW defect causes notable changes in the local ring structure but does not impact the band gap in FG [48]. The inverted F atom is created when one of the F atoms breaks the up-down symmetry of the chair conformation (the orientation of the C-F bond direction alternates between each side of the C layer for adjacent carbons) and binds to the opposite side of the carbon layer. The defect may be created during fluorination, especially when the sides of the carbon layer are not fluorinated at the same rate (e.g., when fluorinating supported graphene). The formation energies of both defects are similar, rather high ($>3\text{eV}$), and independent of the fluorine chemical potential.

Another class of defects arises from edge terminations, which are intrinsic to the layered morphology and atomically thin structure of the material. Edges are created by cleaving the FG sheet along specific crystallographic directions within the (0001) basal plane. Similarly to graphene, there are two high symmetry directions within the (0001) surface plane of FG; cleaving along them creates either an armchair edge or a zigzag edge [49]. We constructed an additional model, a periodic one-dimensional nanostripe serving as a model of an ideal straight edge (Fig. 2). According to our calculation, the zigzag edge is by 2.20 eV per edge formula unit more stable than the armchair edge in the as-cut state (cut out of the FG surface supercell and relaxed). Thus, the zigzag edge

Fig. 1. The structural models of defects in FG; (a) two main conformations of stoichiometric FG, the chair and the boat, (b) C_4F structure (c) the fluorine radical defect V_{F} , (d) the fluorine divacancy $V_{2\text{F}}$, (e) the carbon-and-fluorine vacancy, (f) the Stone-Wales defect and (g) inverted F atom. The carbon atoms are grey and fluorine yellow. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. The structural model of the zigzag edge of FG modeled by one-dimensional nanostripe periodic along the y direction, along the x direction terminated into vacuum by CF_2 on both sides, (a) perspective view and (b) top view.

must be much more abundant in FG samples. However, as-cut edge contains undercoordinated carbon atoms which can be saturated by adsorption of additional fluorine atoms, i.e., by formation of the CF_2 groups at the edge. Our DFT calculation supports this scenario because it shows that creation of the CF_2 group at the zigzag edge is thermodynamically favorable: the formation energy of the CF_2 -terminated edge is lower by 1.88 eV per edge formula unit than the energy of the CF -terminated edge.

3.2. XPS, EPR, and morphological characterization of the real GF samples

We thoroughly characterized two specific FG samples to investigate how the defects discussed in the preceding section manifest experimentally. Before discussing specific structural features, we first address the intricacy of XPS measurement itself, where the lack of standardization leads to inconsistencies in XPS data processing across different laboratories. For instance, the choice of binding energy reference can influence the absolute binding energy value [50]. A common approach is to assign the C 1s peak of adventitious carbon to a certain value (usually 285.0 eV) and use this as the reference. However, this method is problematic because the actual binding energy of such carbon atoms can vary significantly, ranging from 284.08 eV to 286.74 eV [51]. Alternatively, the sample can be deposited onto a gold substrate, with the Au $4f_{7/2}$ peak at 84.0 eV used as reference [50]. However, the challenge extends further because many experimental reports lack a detailed description of the charge correction approach used. This omission makes direct comparison with previously reported XPS values for fluorographene and graphite fluoride unreliable. To mitigate these inaccuracies in binding energy referencing, we recorded our spectra using dual-beam charge compensation of the sample during the measurement. Furthermore, as our XPS results show, the spectra vary substantially depending on whether ion beam etching was applied to the measured area prior to data acquisition.

First, spectra of pristine surfaces were recorded, followed by measurements after ion beam etching to gauge differences between the elemental composition of the surfaces with that of the inner layers. The surface of GFA1 was primarily composed of fluorine (54.9 at. % F, Fig. S6a) and carbon, with no other detected elements. In contrast, the subsurface composition was dominated by carbon (51.2 at. % C, Fig. 3a), with fluorine levels decreasing to 47.8 at. % due to a minor oxygen impurity (1 at. % O). Similarly, the surface of GFC2L consisted mostly of fluorine (56.9 at. % F) with a small nitrogen impurity (0.6 at. % N, Fig. S6b). Below the surface, its composition approached a near C_1F_1 stoichiometry, with minor oxygen (1.2 at. % O) and nitrogen (0.5 at. % N) impurities (Fig. 3b). Overall, XPS measurements of pristine graphite fluoride surfaces tend to overestimate fluorine content. This effect arises from the termination of the individual fluorographene flakes with CF_2 and CF_3 groups [52–54].

More striking differences in the XPS recorded before and after the ion beam etching were observed in the shapes and positions of the C 1s spectral lines. After etching away the surface layer, lower binding energy of C 1s states emerged in both materials. Additionally, the maxima of the C 1s spectral lines for the GFA1 and GFC2L shifted from 289.9 and 289.7 eV, respectively, to 289.5 eV for both materials. A direct comparison of the C 1s and F 1s spectra before and after ion beam etching is presented in Figs. S7 and S8 (Supporting Information). Following ion beam etching, we recorded a binding energy of 289.5 eV for the C 1s state and 688.7 eV for the F 1s state (Table 2), both corresponding to covalent C–F bonds. In contrast, Nair et al. [7], in their original article reporting fluorographene, conducted XPS on large (centimeter-scale) areas of few-layer graphene grown on SiC fluorinated by XeF_2 exposure over two months. Their measurement showed an F peak at 687.7 eV and a C–F peak at 288.5 eV, but the sample was not in a fully fluorinated state. For the graphite fluorides, Kita et al. reported C 1s and F 1s binding energies of 290.4 eV and 689.6 eV, respectively [26]. Wang et al. synthesized single- and few-layer fluorinated graphene sheets from honeycomb graphene oxide as the starting material and reported C 1s peak of 289.7 eV [53].

Besides the main C–F peak, the high-resolution spectra of both samples also show another signal, a pronounced shoulder at ~ 291.5 eV and a broad feature in the 288–284 eV range (Fig. 3c and d). The question arises: what can we learn about the samples from those? The shoulder at ~ 291.5 eV, distinctly visible in the spectrum of GFC2L (Fig. 3d), could be linked to CF_2 groups since these have been reported in literature consistently; Sun et al. [52] reported high-resolution C 1s XPS peaks at 289.0, 291.0, 292.0 eV, which they assigned to covalent C–F, CF_2 , CF_3 bonds, respectively, in FG prepared by solvothermal exfoliation of fluorinated graphite using acetonitrile. Li et al. studied reactivity of fluorographene with amines and fitted $-\text{CF}_2$ at 291.3 eV and $-\text{CF}_3$ at 293.2 eV in their high-resolution C 1s XPS spectrum [54].

Since CF_2 groups are likely concentrated at the edges and wrinkles of FG flakes [55,56], it follows that GFA1 consists of larger and/or less defective $(\text{CF})_n$ domains due to its lower CF_2 and CF_3 content. By this reasoning, GFC2L should comprise FG flakes with smaller particle diameters or a higher density of edge defects incorporating CF_2 moieties. To test this hypothesis, both materials were examined using SEM. The SEM images (Fig. 4) reveal clear structural differences: GFA1 exhibits sharp edges, even in smaller particles, while GFC2L has wrinkled edges, making them effectively longer than those of GFA1. Additionally, smaller GFC2L particles appear more rounded, suggesting the presence of tiny flakes, akin to slices forming a sphere. This structural variation enhances the prominence of edge moieties in GFC2L, further supporting the presence of CF_2 groups.

Additional proof of the more ordered character of GFA1 and high occurrence of CF_2 groups in the GFC2L sample comes from solid-state NMR analysis of both samples (Fig. S4 and S5). While almost half of the ^{19}F nuclei of the GFA1 sample were found in the perfect chair conformation, the GFC2L sample, as described earlier by Walder et al. [20], exhibited a high degree of disorder (38.5 % of the total ^{19}F spectral

Fig. 3. XPS analysis of GFA1 and GFC2L materials. All the spectra shown have been recorded upon ion beam etching. Panels (a) and (b) show survey XPS spectra of GFA1 and GFC2L materials, respectively, with their determined elemental composition in the inset. Panels (c) and (d) contain C 1s HR-XPS spectra of the GFA1 and GFC2L, respectively, partially deconvoluted in accordance with the literature (see text).

Table 2

The calculated XPS binding energies of the C 1s and F 1s in various structures of FG. F 1s near defect refers to the fluorine atoms surrounding a given defect, e.g., F vacancy. For C_4F and $(C_2F)_n$, there are two types of carbon atoms: non-fluorinated carbon and F-bound carbon (in parentheses). The value of graphene was taken from our earlier publication (Ref. [40]).

Model	C 1s	F 1s (near defect)
FG chair (FG _c)	289.4	688.7
FG boat (FG _b)	289.2	689.3
$(C_2F)_n$	289.2 (290.2)	690.5
C_4F	285.5 (288.7)	688.0
V_F	283.0	-(687.0)
V_{2F}	284.9	-(688.5)
V_{CF}	285.4	-(688.1)
Stone-Wales (d_{sw})	289.4	689.7
CF_2 (on edge)	291.5	691.3
F^- adsorbed on graphene graphene	286.5	685.9
	284.3	-

area). However, the content of CF_2 groups in GFC2L was much higher than that reported by Rimsza et al. [19], and also than that found in GFA1. The fluorine bonded in CF_2 groups amounts to 40.3 % of ^{19}F nuclei, which, combined with a minor CF_3 content of 3.6 %, makes the F/C ratio of 1.29 for the GFC2L sample.

Going back to the C 1s envelope interpretation, the broad signal between 284 and 288 eV is more challenging to interpret, except for possible residual sp^2 carbons in the material at around 284 eV. A presence of “semi-ionic” C-F bond at around 288 eV has been reported in

several studies [28,52,57–59]. This term is a functional definition that refers to bond strengths (and corresponding XPS binding energies) that fall between those of a covalent C-F bond, such as in PTFE, and an ionic bond, as found in LiF [60]. In this scenario, the fluorine ion is weakly bound to a planar sp^2 carbon thus not disturbing the electronic conductivity of the graphitic backbone [61]. Owing to that, this feature has been often linked with improved charge-transfer properties of fluorinated carbons in energy storage applications [52,57–59]. However, the term “semi-ionic” bond has been rather inconsistently attributed to the C 1s signals ranging from 287 to 290 eV so its exact nature remains elusive [28].

Even when considering the presence of “semi-ionic” bonds centered around 288 eV, our C 1s spectra are still not resolved between the regions 285–287 eV (Fig. 3c and d). Given the low impurity content in the samples, it is possible that a part of signal in the 284–288 eV range may arise from other defects, such as vacancies. Since V_F and V_{CF} vacancies possess an unpaired spin in their ground state, their presence in FG can be confirmed using EPR spectroscopy. The samples were measured in powder form, with EPR tube loading maintained at 8 mg to ensure a good signal-to-noise ratio. All measurements were conducted under identical experimental conditions, allowing for a direct comparison of the resonance signatures of GFA1 and GFC2L in terms of signal intensity and overall line shape characteristics. Both materials exhibited EPR signals consistent with the presence of organic-based radical species (Fig. 5a). In the case of GFC2L, the observed resonance signature at $g_{eff} = 2.00$ is dominated by the presence of spin-coupled centers that can be interpreted as populated triplet states ($S = 1$). This result is partly in agreement with previous EPR analysis performed on commercial C_1F_{1+x}

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of GFA1 (top row) and GFC2L (bottom row) materials.

Fig. 5. Continuous wave X-band (9.07–9.08 GHz) EPR spectra of GFA1 and GFC2L (a), recorded at $T = 90$ K. Panel (b) shows the EPR spectrum of GFC2L recorded at higher gain.

samples, material that was provided by different supplier [23]. Compared to the previous EPR spectra (c.f. Fig. S12) [23], here the presence of isolated and spin uncorrelated defects (isolated $S = 1/2$ centers) in GFC2L is limited. This hypothesis invokes the presence of higher concentration of V_{CF} vacancies that contain pair of antiferromagnetically coupled electrons ($S = 0$). Alternatively, such signal can be an outcome of a mutual interaction between the two V_F vacancies with small through-space distances. In the case of GFA1, the contribution of triplet states remains substantially invariant with respect to GFC2L. This effect can be clearly seen by comparing directly the intensity of the resonance wings developing symmetrically with respect to the strong central line at $g_{\text{eff}} = 2.00$ in both GFC2L and GFA1 (Fig. 5a). The strong resonance central line is associated with isolated spin-containing defects that can be represented by dangling bonds on sp^3 carbon atoms (V_F). The amount of these $S = 1/2$ species is high in GFA1 compared to GFC2L. Such a feature can translate into the population of mid-gap energy states [11], and can therefore mirror the observed narrowing of the band-gap (Fig. S2) and contribute to the drastic change in the sample color (Fig. S1). These EPR results indicate that even minor compositional differences (as seen in Fig. 3 for XPS) can significantly impact the electronic properties of the systems. Overall, the EPR data suggest that V_{CF} vacancies dominate in GFC2L, as evidenced by the observed triplet signal. While this triplet signal is also present in GFA1, its spectrum is primarily characterized by a doublet signal associated with V_F point

defects. Thus, both materials contain magnetic vacancies; however, the extent to which their presence is reflected in the XPS spectra remains not fully resolved.

3.3. Theoretical assignment of structural features in XPS spectra

The computed binding energies for the C 1s state equal to 289.4 eV and 688.7 eV for the F 1s state (Table 2). These values align perfectly with our experimental observations, where we recorded binding energies of 289.5 eV for the C 1s state and 688.7 eV for the F 1s after ion beam etching. This agreement validates the reliability of our theoretical approach, allowing us to calculate various structural motifs in FG to provide consistent guidelines for interpreting the experimental spectra. It must be noted that the binding energies of CF, C_2F , and C_4F were calculated earlier by Cavallari et al. [32]. However, in contrast to our all-electron approach, Cavallari et al. employed projected augmented waves in VASP to calculate binding energies - in such an approach, the other core and semi-core electrons are not allowed to relax due to the presence of a core-hole, which causes an error in the calculated binding energies. For instance, they reported the C 1s binding energy of 285.9 eV for perfect FG [32], which is too low a value compared to the experiment.

A catalogue of XPS binding energies of various structural features of fluorinated graphenes is listed in Table 2. The boat conformation is

indistinguishable from the chair conformation in XPS, as their binding energies are too close. The same binding energy value was also found for the C–C sp^3 bonds of poly(dicarbon monofluoride) $(C_2F)_n$ in F-diamane structure. However, our high-resolution spectrum of GFC2L reveals a pronounced shoulder at ~ 291.2 eV (Fig. 3d), which we attribute to CF_2 groups at the edges (see previous section). To test this hypothesis, we employed the periodic nanostripe model of CF_2 -terminated zigzag edge in FG. The calculated C 1s binding energy for this CF_2 group is 291.5 eV, in excellent agreement with the experimental peak position, further supporting this structural assignment. This strong agreement with experimental results also reinforces our argument that the zigzag edges terminated by CF_2 groups are the dominant edge type in FG, as they exhibit the more favorable formation energy.

When considering point defects, the radical defect V_F exhibits a binding energy of 283.0 eV, which is lower than any other carbon species in our study, making its detection by XPS theoretically possible. If a neighboring fluorine is released, forming V_{2F} defect, the binding energy shifts to 284.9 eV due to the local restoration of carbon atoms into a planar sp^2 -bonded configuration. This signal would however overlap with that of sp^2 carbon (calculated value for graphene: 284.3 eV, see Ref. [40]), which is also expected to arise from less fluorinated (or partially defluorinated) regions of the sample. Similarly, the signal from a Stone-Wales defect would coincide with that of pristine FG, as the C 1s binding energy of carbon atoms within five- and seven-membered rings is 289.4 eV, i.e., the same as that of perfect chair FG.

Interestingly, none of thus far discussed features account for the residual signal observed between 285.5 and 287 eV in our XPS spectra (Fig. 3c and d). As discussed above, some of experimental XPS studies on graphite fluorides have occasionally reported a peak around 287–288 eV, often attributed to the “semi-ionic” C–F bond [28,52,62]. This peak has been associated with the non-fluorinated C atoms linked to fluorinated ones (C–CF species), though the assignment remains somewhat ambiguous [28]. For instance, for $(C_2F)_n$ in the F-diamane structure, the calculated binding energy of non-fluorinated and fluorinated carbon is 289.2 eV and 290.2 eV, respectively (Table 2). These values are similar to the binding energy of fully fluorinated FG, corroborating studies on the short-range structure of graphite fluoride $(C_2F)_n$, which revealed that the presumed semi-ionic C–F bonding in these samples was substantially covalent [63].

Since no previously considered carbon species fully explain this signal, we explored an alternative scenario: a single fluorine ion adsorbed onto a graphene sheet, modeled using a 6×6 supercell. The ionic interaction pulls the neighboring carbon atom out of graphene plane, disrupting its sp^2 hybridization. This contradicts the generally assumed idea of a semi-ionic bond preserving the sp^2 character of the carbon thus not influencing the electric conductivity of graphene [61]. The resulting C–F bond length is 1.65 Å, much longer than the covalent bond of 1.37 Å in the chair conformation FG. This finding is in a good agreement with the previously reported value of 1.61 Å [64]. The C 1s binding energy of the fluorinated carbon atom nearest to the F anion is 286.5 eV, suggesting that F ions adsorbed onto graphitic regions of the sample could contribute to the broad signal in the XPS spectra. Additionally, in the C_4F structure, where $CF-C=CF$ motifs are present, the non-fluorinated carbon exhibits a C 1s binding energy of 285.5 eV, falling between that of a sp^2 carbon and F ions, while the fluorinated counterpart has a C 1s binding energy of 288.7 eV. These values fit well within the 285–288 eV range and, thus, their convolution could produce observed signal. Importantly, these structural motifs are well supported by prior studies. It has been established that at low fluorine concentration (correlated with a low treatment temperature) a graphitic structure can be preserved, with mainly intercalated fluoride ions [32]. Following fluorine intercalation, C_4F retains lamellar graphitic structure [65] and has been identified as the lowest-energy configuration for one-sided fluorination [66]. C_4F has also been identified at the core domains of the particles when the diffusion of fluorine during the fluorination process is limited [31,32].

With the theoretically assessed binding energy values in hand, we can revisit the deconvolution of our experimental spectra of GFA1 and GFC2L materials. For feasible deconvolution, in several cases, multiple structural features had to be merged into one component due to their spectral position proximity. Our approach is described in Table S1, Supporting Information. The originally unassigned region of the C 1s spectra is dominated by components representing the V_{2F} and V_{CF} vacancies, sp^2 carbons of C_4F structures, and the ionic F species adsorbed on graphene (Fig. S10). C–F covalent bonds of C_4F at 288.7 eV almost coincide with the main peak at 289.5 eV, which comprises carbon from several different structural motifs: hexagonal and boat conformation of polycarbon monofluoride, Stone-Wales defect, and sp^3 C–C atoms of $(C_2F)_n$.

3.4. Infra-red spectroscopy

In the pristine graphene, there are two equivalent atoms per unit cell, resulting in six normal modes for the zone center. However, the ring stretching vibrations are IR inactive due to the symmetry of the system, rendering pristine defect-free graphene completely IR silent [67]. In pristine fluorographene, changed symmetry dictates that there should appear two infrared-active modes, A_{2u} and two-fold degenerate E_u mode [68]. These two IR-active modes indeed appear in the calculated spectrum of perfect FG (Fig. 6). The computed frequencies for the A_{2u} and E_u modes of chair FG are 1228 cm^{-1} and 316 cm^{-1} , respectively. For the chair conformation of FG, we also calculated the IR spectra of various point defects to determine whether any defect-specific signatures could be identified. However, detecting point defects via IR spectroscopy appears unlikely, as their presence does not significantly alter the spectral pattern of perfect FG (Fig. S11). Neither the V_F defect nor the Stone-Wales defect introduces new IR-active vibrational modes, making their spectra indistinguishable from that of perfect FG. The inverted F defect exhibits a new vibrational mode at 333 cm^{-1} , but this peak is too close to the E_u mode of perfect FG at 316 cm^{-1} to be clearly resolvable. In the case of the V_{2F} defect, new IR-active vibrations emerge at 700 and 950 cm^{-1} , however, their intensities are too low to be reliably detected.

Despite its limitations in detecting point defects, IR spectroscopy remains a valuable tool for identifying structural conformations in FG. The boat conformation of FG exhibits an orthorhombic symmetry, which results in the appearance of a new IR-active mode at 620 cm^{-1} in addition to the primary mode at 1228 cm^{-1} (Fig. 6). This peak at 620 cm^{-1} serves as a distinctive fingerprint of the boat conformation. However, we found no evidence of this signal in our experimental spectra or in literature. This supports the conclusion based on the formation energy calculation (section Defects in fluorographene and their formation energy), that the boat structure is metastable. Nonetheless, it may still exist in the form of small domains or as a byproduct of defect formation, particularly in cases where the fluorine atom arrangement is altered, such as in the presence of Stone-Wales defects or fluorine inversion.

Notably, C_4F exhibits an IR spectrum distinct from that of pristine FG. While the main IR peak at $\sim 1230\text{ cm}^{-1}$ remains, additional satellite peaks emerge at 538 and 923 cm^{-1} . These new IR signals arise due to partial rehybridization of the carbon atoms to sp^2 , and a significant elongation of C–F bonds compared to FG. In the preceding section, we proposed that C_4F phase contributes to the broad signal observed between 285 and 288 eV in our XPS spectra. The remaining question is whether this phase can be experimentally identified through IR spectroscopy.

To investigate this further, we measured experimental IR spectra of both samples (Fig. 7). For the well-ordered sample GFA1, the peaks corresponding to the A_{2u} and E_u modes are clearly resolved. The A_{2u} peak exhibits a maximum at 1195 cm^{-1} . While this wavenumber is slightly lower than the calculated value (1228 cm^{-1}), the experimental peak is relatively broad. It is important to note that the experimental vibrational frequencies can vary depending on the character of the

Fig. 6. The computed IR spectra of various structural forms of FG; the chair conformation of FG, the boat conformation, C_2F structure as a model of one-sided fluorination, and the partially fluorinated structure C_4F .

Fig. 7. Infrared spectra of GFA1 (a) and GFC2L (b). The calculated IR spectrum of the $(C_2F)_n$ structure (c). The calculated IR spectrum of the FG nanostripe exposing on both sides the zigzag edges terminated by CF_2 groups (d).

sample and preparation method. For instance, previous studies have reported values of 1204 cm^{-1} for nanocrystalline graphite monofluoride [69] and 1211 cm^{-1} for graphene fluorinated by XeF_2 [70]. While the E_u mode is distinctly resolved at 330 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the GFA1 sample (Fig. 7a), it is absent in the spectrum of the more defective GFC2L sample (Fig. 7b). Notably, although the E_u mode was experimentally confirmed by Kita et al., in 1979 [26], it is rarely utilized in modern IR analyses of graphite fluorides.

Even more importantly, the spectrum of GFA1 exhibits peaks at 540 cm^{-1} and 967 cm^{-1} , which our calculations identified as characteristic fingerprints of the C_4F structure (c.f. Fig. 6). This confirms the presence of C_4F domains in the GFA1 sample. To explore the possible presence of other low-fluorination regions, we calculated the IR spectrum of $(C_2F)_n$ in the F-diamane structure (Fig. 7c). The computed spectrum reveals

new peaks at 1359 cm^{-1} and 951 cm^{-1} , resulting in four IR active modes in the structure. Four IR active modes of $(C_2F)_n$ agree with the symmetry analysis by Chen et al., who derived $3A_{1g} + 3A_{2u} + 3E_u + 3E_g$ multiplicities for the modes at the zone center, out of which four modes are IR active [71]. Our calculated values of the vibrational frequencies are slightly higher than those reported by Chen et al. [71], presumably due to the different exchange-correlation functional, nevertheless closely match the peaks at 1348 cm^{-1} and 939 cm^{-1} observed in the GFA1 spectrum. Moreover, the assignment of the band at 939 cm^{-1} to $(C_2F)_n$ is in agreement with recent experimental report on the well-ordered single phase $(C_2F)_n$ displaying an IR band at 940 cm^{-1} [72]. The close agreement of theory and experiments implies that GFA1 contains also well-ordered $(C_2F)_n$ regions, albeit their relative amount is low, because $^{13}C^{19}F$ -decoupled MAS solid-state NMR of GFA1 detected very low

content (7.1 % of the total spectral area) of this phase (Fig. S5).

Lastly, our XPS results indicated the presence of CF₂ groups, likely residing at the edges and wrinkles of FG flakes. Based on that, we calculated the IR spectrum of the periodic nanostripe with the zigzag edge terminated by CF₂ on both sides (see previous sections for details). The computed spectrum reveals that while the main A_{2u} peak remains at the same wavenumber as in the perfectly periodic FG (1233 cm⁻¹), the E_u mode is blueshifted to 354 cm⁻¹, and several new peaks emerge (Fig. 7d). Notably, a strong vibration at 1329 cm⁻¹ appears, which fits a shoulder at ~1315 cm⁻¹ in the experimental spectrum of GFC2L (Fig. 7b). Additionally, the calculated vibration at 1059 cm⁻¹ corresponds well with a weak mode at 1078 cm⁻¹ in the GFA1 spectrum (Fig. 7a) and a shoulder in the range between 1000 and 1100 cm⁻¹ in the GFC2L spectrum. These two spectral features may serve as a fingerprint of CF₂ presence.

4. Conclusions

In summary, the results presented here provide a solid foundation for identifying the structural features of graphite fluorides and fluorographene from spectroscopy data under support of theoretical calculations. XPS analysis of two commercial fluorinated carbon samples reveals that the spectra must be recorded after discharging the sample surface, such as through ion discharging. Surface etching before XPS measurements is essential for resolving all structural features. For perfect FG in the chair conformation, our DFT calculations revealed the binding energy of 289.4 eV for the C 1s and 688.7 eV for the F 1s, which align perfectly with our experimental results after ion beam etching. This allows us to use the calculations to build the catalogue of XPS energies: the boat conformation has similar binding energies, making it indistinguishable from the chair form in XPS. The presence of CF₂ groups can be identified by the C 1s binding energy of 291.5 eV and F 1s of 691.3 eV. These moieties are commonly associated with edges and wrinkles on a sample's surface. Our calculations support this, showing that the zigzag edge is more stable than the armchair edge of FG, with CF₂ being the most stable termination of the zigzag edge. Detecting point defects and less fluorinated regions via XPS is challenging because their signals overlap with those of either pristine FG or sp² carbon. A notable exception is the fluorine vacancy V_F which exhibits unusually low C 1s binding energy of 283.0 eV. Interestingly, a broad signal was recorded in our XPS spectra between 285 and 288 eV, an unusual range. Our calculations suggest that in the C₄F structure, the non-fluorinated carbon exhibits a C 1s binding energy of 285.5 eV, while its fluorinated counterpart has a binding energy of 288.7 eV. These values fit within the 285–288 eV range and their convolution with the signal from fluoride ions adsorbed on graphitic regions could explain the observed broad feature.

IR spectroscopy provides additional structural identification complementary to XPS. For fluorographene in the chair conformation, there are two infrared active modes, A_{2u} and two-fold degenerate E_u, with the calculated frequencies of 1228 cm⁻¹ and 316 cm⁻¹, respectively. The boat conformation would introduce an additional IR-active mode at 620 cm⁻¹ due to its orthorhombic symmetry. CF₂ edge groups exhibit characteristic vibrations at 1329 cm⁻¹ and at 1078 cm⁻¹. The C₄F structure displays satellite peaks at 538 and 923 cm⁻¹, both of which are evident in the experimental spectra. Furthermore, (C₂F)_n in the F-diamond structure can be identified by vibrations at 1359 and 951 cm⁻¹ in addition to the main peak at 1230 cm⁻¹. The traces of these vibration modes can be also identified in the experimental spectrum of the GFA1 sample. These results indicate that even nominally fully fluorinated graphite/fluorographene contains partially fluorinated regions, which may significantly impact its reactivity.

Our findings underscore the powerful synergy between XPS and IR spectroscopy in enabling precise identification of key structural features in graphite fluoride when combined with quantum mechanical calculations. Notably, we highlight the untapped potential of IR spectroscopy

at mid-to-low frequencies, an often-overlooked yet highly effective tool for distinguishing structural motifs—particularly those arising from partially fluorinated domains. Looking ahead, the integration of theoretical modeling with experimental techniques, enhanced by data-driven approaches and machine learning, holds immense promise for revolutionizing structural assignment in complex materials. This interdisciplinary approach paves the way for deeper insights and more accurate characterizations, driving innovation in materials science.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Petr Lazar: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Vítězslav Hrubý:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Martin Petr:** Investigation, Data curation. **Zdeněk Baďura:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Giorgio Zoppellaro:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Michal Otyepka:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

MO has share in ATOMIVER, Ltd. company. Other authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

We thank Jiří Hošek for the SEM imaging, and Josef Kašík for the XRD measurements. The work was supported by the Czech Science Foundation (GAČR), project No. GA22-33284S. This article has been produced with the financial support of the European Union under the REFRESH - Research Excellence for Region Sustainability and High-tech Industries project number CZ.10.03.01/00/22_003/0000048 via the Operational Programme Just Transition. We acknowledge support from the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic through the e-INFRA CZ (ID:90254). We also acknowledge support from ERDF/ESF project TECHSCALE (No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004587). Support from IGA_PrF_2025_003 is also acknowledged. Additional funding was provided by the Research Infrastructure Nano-EnviCz, supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic under Project No. LM2023066.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2025.120567>.

References

- [1] P.V. Klimov, J. Kelly, Z. Chen, M. Neeley, A. Megrant, B. Burkett, R. Barends, K. Arya, B. Chiaro, Y. Chen, A. Dunsworth, A. Fowler, B. Foxen, C. Gidney, M. Giustina, R. Graff, T. Huang, E. Jeffrey, E. Lucero, J.Y. Mutus, O. Naaman, C. Neill, C. Quintana, P. Roushan, D. Sank, A. Vainsencher, J. Wenner, T.C. White, S. Boixo, R. Babbush, V.N. Smelyanskiy, H. Neven, J.M. Martinis, Fluctuations of energy-relaxation times in superconducting qubits, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 121 (9) (2018) 090502.
- [2] N.P. de Leon, K.M. Itoh, D. Kim, K.K. Mehta, T.E. Northup, H. Paik, B.S. Palmer, N. Samarth, S. Sangtawesin, D.W. Steuerman, Materials challenges and opportunities for quantum computing hardware, *Science* 372 (6539) (2021) eabb2823.

- [3] O. Ruff, O. Bretschneider, Die Reaktionsprodukte der verschiedenen Kohlenstoffformen mit Fluor II (Kohlenstoff-monofluorid), *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.* 217 (1) (1934) 1–18.
- [4] H. Groult, A. Tressaud, Use of inorganic fluorinated materials in lithium batteries and in energy conversion systems, *Chem. Commun.* 54 (81) (2018) 11375–11382.
- [5] K. Fan, X. Chen, X. Wang, X. Liu, Y. Liu, W. Lai, X. Liu, Toward excellent tribological performance as oil-based lubricant additive: particular tribological behavior of fluorinated graphene, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 10 (34) (2018) 28828–28838.
- [6] Z. Yang, L. Wang, W. Sun, S. Li, T. Zhu, W. Liu, G. Liu, Superhydrophobic epoxy coating modified by fluorographene used for anti-corrosion and self-cleaning, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 401 (2017) 146–155.
- [7] R.R. Nair, W. Ren, R. Jalil, I. Riaz, V.G. Kravets, L. Britnell, P. Blake, F. Schedin, A. S. Mayorov, S. Yuan, M.I. Katsnelson, H.-M. Cheng, W. Strupinski, L.G. Bulusheva, A.V. Okotrub, I.V. Grigorieva, A.N. Grigorenko, K.S. Novoselov, A.K. Geim, Fluorographene: a two-dimensional counterpart of teflon, *Small* 6 (24) (2010) 2877–2884.
- [8] R. Zboril, F. Karlický, A.B. Bourlinos, T.A. Steriotis, A.K. Stubos, V. Georgakilas, K. Šafářová, D. Jancík, C. Trapalis, M. Otyepka, Graphene fluoride: a stable stoichiometric graphene derivative and its chemical conversion to graphene, *Small* 6 (24) (2010) 2885–2891.
- [9] F. Karlický, M. Otyepka, Band gaps and optical spectra from single- and double-layer fluorographene to graphite fluoride: many-body effects and excitonic states, *Ann. Phys.* 526 (9–10) (2014) 408–414.
- [10] M. Dubecký, F. Karlický, S. Minářík, L. Mitas, Fundamental gap of fluorographene by many-body GW and fixed-node diffusion monte carlo methods, *J. Chem. Phys.* 153 (18) (2020) 184706.
- [11] V. Hrubý, L. Zdražil, J. Džibelová, V. Šedajová, A. Bakandritsos, P. Lazar, M. Otyepka, Unveiling the true band gap of fluorographene and its origins by teaming theory and experiment, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 587 (2022) 152839.
- [12] N. Sharma, M. Dubois, K. Guérin, V. Pischedda, S. Radescu, Fluorinated (Nano) Carbons: CF electrodes and CF-Based batteries, *Energy Technol.* 9 (4) (2021) 2000605.
- [13] A. Bakandritsos, M. Pykal, P. Błoński, P. Jakubec, D.D. Chronopoulos, K. Poláková, V. Georgakilas, K. Čépe, O. Tomanec, V. Ranc, A.B. Bourlinos, R. Zboril, M. Otyepka, Cyanographene and graphene acid: emerging derivatives enabling high-yield and selective functionalization of graphene, *ACS Nano* 11 (3) (2017) 2982–2991.
- [14] V. Urbanová, K. Holá, A.B. Bourlinos, K. Čépe, A. Ambrosi, A.H. Loo, M. Pumera, F. Karlický, M. Otyepka, R. Zboril, Thiofluorographene–hydrophilic graphene derivative with semiconducting and genosensing properties, *Adv. Mater.* 27 (14) (2015) 2305–2310.
- [15] R. Stine, J.W. Ciszek, D.E. Barlow, W.-K. Lee, J.T. Robinson, P.E. Sheehan, High-density amine-terminated monolayers formed on fluorinated CVD-grown graphene, *Langmuir* 28 (21) (2012) 7957–7961.
- [16] C. Bosch-Navarro, M. Walker, N.R. Wilson, J.P. Rourke, Covalent modification of exfoliated fluorographene with nitrogen functionalities, *J. Mater. Chem. C* 3 (29) (2015) 7627–7631.
- [17] D.D. Chronopoulos, A. Bakandritsos, P. Lazar, M. Pykal, K. Čépe, R. Zboril, M. Otyepka, High-yield alkylation and arylation of graphene via grignard reaction with fluorographene, *Chem. Mater.* 29 (3) (2017) 926–930.
- [18] W. Rüdorff, G. Rüdorff, Zur Konstitution des Kohlenstoff-Monofluorids, *Z. Anorg. Chem.* 253 (5–6) (1947) 281–296.
- [19] J.M. Rimsza, B.J. Walder, T.M. Alam, Influence of polymorphs and local defect structures on NMR parameters of graphite fluorides, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 125 (4) (2021) 2699–2712.
- [20] B.J. Walder, T.M. Alam, Modes of disorder in poly(carbon monofluoride), *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 143 (30) (2021) 11714–11733.
- [21] K.-J. Jeon, Z. Lee, E. Pollak, L. Moreschini, A. Bostwick, C.-M. Park, R. Mendelsberg, V. Radmilovic, R. Kostecki, T.J. Richardson, E. Rotenberg, Fluorographene: a wide bandgap semiconductor with ultraviolet luminescence, *ACS Nano* 5 (2) (2011) 1042–1046.
- [22] V. Mazánek, O. Jankovský, J. Luxa, D. Sedmidubský, Z. Janoušek, F. Šembera, M. Mikulics, Z. Sofer, Tuning of fluorine content in graphene: towards large-scale production of stoichiometric fluorographene, *Nanoscale* 7 (32) (2015) 13646–13655.
- [23] M. Medved, G. Zoppellaro, J. Ugolotti, D. Matochova, P. Lazar, T. Pospisil, A. Bakandritsos, J. Tucek, R. Zboril, M. Otyepka, Reactivity of fluorographene is triggered by point defects: beyond the perfect 2D world, *Nanoscale* 10 (10) (2018) 4696–4707.
- [24] M.S. Tacca, M.B. Plenio, Group theoretical and ab initio description of color center candidates in fluorographene, *Phys. Rev. B* 108 (10) (2023) 104102.
- [25] G. Zoppellaro, M. Medved, V. Hrubý, R. Zboril, M. Otyepka, P. Lazar, Solvent controlled generation of spin active polarons in two-dimensional material under UV light irradiation, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 146 (22) (2024) 15010–15018.
- [26] Y. Kita, N. Watanabe, Y. Fujii, Chemical composition and crystal structure of graphite fluoride, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 101 (14) (1979) 3832–3841.
- [27] T. Mallouk, N. Bartlett, Reversible intercalation of graphite by fluorine: a new bifluoride, C₁₂H₂F₂, and graphite fluorides, CF (5 > x > 2), *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.* (3) (1983) 103–105.
- [28] Y. Sato, K. Itoh, R. Hagiwara, T. Fukunaga, Y. Ito, On the so-called “semi-ionic” C-F bond character in fluorine–GIC, *Carbon* 42 (15) (2004) 3243–3249.
- [29] H. Touhara, K. Kadono, Y. Fujii, N. Watanabe, On the structure of graphite fluoride, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.* 544 (1) (1987) 7–20.
- [30] Y. Sato, K. Itoh, R. Hagiwara, T. Fukunaga, Y. Ito, Short-range structures of poly (dicarbon monofluoride) (C₂F)_n and poly(carbon monofluoride) (CF)_n, *Carbon* 42 (14) (2004) 2897–2903.
- [31] B.J. Walder, N.B. Schorr, L.B. Brunke, M.P. Siegal, T.M. Alam, K.J. Fritzsche, T. N. Lambert, Composites of (C₄F)_n and (CF)_n synthesized by uncatalyzed fluorination of graphite, *Solids* (2022) 237–257.
- [32] C. Cavallari, M. Brunelli, S. Radescu, M. Dubois, N. Batisse, G.B.M. Vaughan, H. E. Fischer, V. Pischedda, Structural and electronic changes in graphite fluorides as a function of fluorination rate: an XRS, PDF and DFT study, *Carbon* 147 (2019) 1–8.
- [33] P.E. Blochl, Projector augmented-wave method, *Phys. Rev. B* 50 (24) (1994) 17953–17979.
- [34] G. Kresse, D. Joubert, From ultrasoft pseudopotentials to the projector augmented-wave method, *Phys. Rev. B* 59 (3) (1999) 1758–1775.
- [35] J.W. Furness, A.D. Kaplan, J. Ning, J.P. Perdew, J. Sun, Accurate and numerically efficient rSCAN meta-generalized gradient approximation, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 11 (19) (2020) 8208–8215.
- [36] J. Sun, A. Ruzsinszky, J.P. Perdew, Strongly constrained and appropriately normed semilocal density functional, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 115 (3) (2015) 036402.
- [37] H. Euchner, A. Groß, Predicting accurate phonon spectra: an improved description of lattice dynamics in thermoelectric clathrates based on the SCAN Meta-GGA functional, *Chem. Mater.* 31 (7) (2019) 2571–2576.
- [38] K. David, B. Tomáš, H. Jürgen, A density-functional study of the adsorption of methane-thiol on the (111) surfaces of the Ni-group metals: II. Vibrational spectroscopy, *J. Phys. Condens. Matter* 22 (26) (2010) 265006.
- [39] V. Blum, R. Gehrke, F. Hanke, P. Havu, V. Havu, X. Ren, K. Reuter, M. Scheffler, Ab initio molecular simulations with numeric atom-centered orbitals, *Comput. Phys. Commun.* 180 (11) (2009) 2175–2196.
- [40] P. Lazar, R. Mach, M. Otyepka, Spectroscopic fingerprints of graphitic, pyrrolic, pyridinic, and chemisorbed nitrogen in N-Doped graphene, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 123 (16) (2019) 10695–10702.
- [41] P. Lazar, E. Otyepkova, F. Karlický, K. Cepe, M. Otyepka, The surface and structural properties of graphite fluoride, *Carbon* 94 (2015) 804–809.
- [42] L. Zhang, Z. Zhang, X.a. Gao, S.J. Matlan, N.A. Taha, The preparations of fluorographene nanosheets and research in tribological properties in high vacuum, *Materials* 16 (2023) 3929.
- [43] L.B. Ebert, J.I. Brauman, R.A. Huggins, Carbon monofluoride, Evidence for a structure containing an infinite array of cyclohexane boats, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 96 (25) (1974) 7841–7842.
- [44] D.T. Clark, J. Peeling, Applications of ESCA to polymer chemistry. XII. Structure and bonding in commercially produced fluorographites, *Journal of Polymer Science: Polymer Chemistry Edition* 14 (12) (1976) 2941–2967.
- [45] R.R. Nair, M. Sepioni, I.L. Tsai, O. Lehtinen, J. Keinonen, A.V. Krashennnikov, T. Thomson, A.K. Geim, I.V. Grigorieva, Spin-half paramagnetism in graphene induced by point defects, *Nat. Phys.* 8 (3) (2012) 199–202.
- [46] J. Cai, A. Retzker, F. Jelezko, M.B. Plenio, A large-scale quantum simulator on a diamond surface at room temperature, *Nat. Phys.* 9 (3) (2013) 168–173.
- [47] N. Watanabe, T. Nakajima, H. Touhara, Graphite Fluorides, Elsevier, 1988.
- [48] F. Karlický, M. Otyepka, Band gaps and optical spectra of chlorographene, fluorographene and graphene from G₀W₀, G₀W₁ and GW calculations on top of PBE and HSE06 orbitals, *J. Chem. Theor. Comput.* 9 (9) (2013) 4155–4164.
- [49] K. Nakada, M. Fujita, G. Dresselhaus, M.S. Dresselhaus, Edge state in graphene ribbons: nanometer size effect and edge shape dependence, *Phys. Rev. B* 54 (24) (1996) 17954–17961.
- [50] Y.-G. Lei, K.-M. Ng, L.-T. Weng, C.-M. Chan, L. Li, XPS C 1s binding energies for fluoro-carbon–hydrocarbon microblock copolymers, *Surf. Interface Anal.* 35 (10) (2003) 852–855.
- [51] G. Greczynski, L. Hultman, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy: towards reliable binding energy referencing, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 107 (2020) 100591.
- [52] C. Sun, Y. Feng, Y. Li, C. Qin, Q. Zhang, W. Feng, Solvothermally exfoliated fluorographene for high-performance lithium primary batteries, *Nanoscale* 6 (5) (2014) 2634–2641.
- [53] X. Wang, Y. Dai, J. Gao, J. Huang, B. Li, C. Fan, J. Yang, X. Liu, High-yield production of highly fluorinated graphene by direct heating fluorination of graphene-oxide, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 5 (17) (2013) 8294–8299.
- [54] B. Li, T. He, Z. Wang, Z. Cheng, Y. Liu, T. Chen, W. Lai, X. Wang, X. Liu, Chemical reactivity of C–F bonds attached to graphene with diamines depending on their nature and location, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 18 (26) (2016) 17495–17505.
- [55] M. Herraiz, M. Dubois, N. Batisse, S. Hajjar-Garreau, L. Simon, Large-scale synthesis of fluorinated graphene by rapid thermal exfoliation of highly fluorinated graphite, *Dalton Trans.* 47 (13) (2018) 4596–4606.
- [56] M. Murakami, K. Matsumoto, R. Hagiwara, Y. Matsuo, ¹³C/¹⁹F high-resolution solid-state NMR studies on layered carbon-fluorine compounds, *Carbon* 138 (2018) 179–187.
- [57] J. Zheng, Y. Lin, C. Du, X. Chen, J. Li, Y. Zheng, Q. Feng, Z. Huang, Fluorine-doped MnO@fluorographene with high conductivity for improved capacity and prolonged cycling stability of lithium-ion anode, *J. Alloys Compd.* 945 (2023) 169255.
- [58] Y. Peng, Y. Liu, R. Ali, J. Ma, J. Hou, X. Yang, X. Jian, Air plasma-induced carbon fluoride enabling active CF bonds for double-high energy/power densities of Li/CF_x primary battery, *J. Alloys Compd.* 905 (2022) 164151.
- [59] T. Jin, J. Chen, C. Wang, Y. Qian, L. Lu, Facile synthesis of fluorine-doped graphene aerogel with rich semi-ionic C–F bonds for high-performance supercapacitor application, *J. Mater. Sci.* 55 (26) (2020) 12103–12113.
- [60] H. Touhara, F. Okino, Property control of carbon materials by fluorination, *Carbon* 38 (2) (2000) 241–267.

- [61] W. Feng, P. Long, Y. Feng, Y. Li, Two-dimensional fluorinated graphene: synthesis, structures, properties and applications, *Adv. Sci.* 3 (7) (2016) 1500413.
- [62] P.F. Fulvio, S.S. Brown, J. Adcock, R.T. Mayes, B. Guo, X.-G. Sun, S.M. Mahurin, G. M. Veith, S. Dai, Low-temperature fluorination of soft-templated mesoporous carbons for a high-power lithium/carbon fluoride battery, *Chem. Mater.* 23 (20) (2011) 4420–4427.
- [63] V. Pischedda, S. Radescu, M. Dubois, N. Batisse, F. Balima, C. Cavallari, L. Cardenas, Experimental and DFT high pressure study of fluorinated graphite (C₂F)_n, *Carbon* 114 (2017) 690–699.
- [64] S. Zhou, S.D. Sherpa, D.W. Hess, A. Bongiorno, Chemical bonding of partially fluorinated graphene, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 118 (45) (2014) 26402–26408.
- [65] V. Pischedda, S. Radescu, M. Dubois, C. Cavallari, N. Batisse, F. Balima, Fluorine-graphite intercalation compound (C₄F)_n at high pressure: experimental and theoretical study, *Carbon* 127 (2018) 384–391.
- [66] J.T. Robinson, J.S. Burgess, C.E. Junkermeier, S.C. Badescu, T.L. Reinecke, F. K. Perkins, M.K. Zhalutdniov, J.W. Baldwin, J.C. Culbertson, P.E. Sheehan, E. S. Snow, Properties of fluorinated graphene films, *Nano Lett.* 10 (8) (2010) 3001–3005.
- [67] T. Humberto, L. Ruitao, T. Mauricio, S.D. Mildred, The role of defects and doping in 2D graphene sheets and 1D nanoribbons, *Rep. Prog. Phys.* 75 (6) (2012) 062501.
- [68] H. Peelaers, A.D. Hernández-Nieves, O. Leenaerts, B. Partoens, F.M. Peeters, Vibrational properties of graphene fluoride and graphane, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 98 (5) (2011) 051914.
- [69] B. Wang, J.R. Sparks, H.R. Gutierrez, F. Okino, Q. Hao, Y. Tang, V.H. Crespi, J. O. Sofo, J. Zhu, Photoluminescence from nanocrystalline graphite monofluoride, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 97 (14) (2010) 141915.
- [70] Y. Wang, W.C. Lee, K.K. Manga, P.K. Ang, J. Lu, Y.P. Liu, C.T. Lim, K.P. Loh, Fluorinated graphene for promoting neuro-induction of stem cells, *Adv. Mater.* 24 (31) (2012) 4285–4290.
- [71] X. Chen, M. Dubois, S. Radescu, A. Rawal, C. Zhao, Liquid-phase exfoliation of F-diamane-like nanosheets, *Carbon* 175 (2021) 124–130.
- [72] V. Nesvizhevsky, K. Henry, L. Dauga, B. Clavier, S. Le Floch, E. Lychagin, A. Muzychka, A. Nezhvanov, V. Pischedda, C. Teander, K. Turlybekuly, S. Radescu, B. Vigolo, S. Cahen, C. Héroul, J. Ghanbaja, K. Zhernenkov, M. Dubois, Poly (dicarbon monofluoride) (C₂F)_n bridges the neutron reflectivity gap, *Carbon* 227 (2024) 119249.